

MECHANISMS GENERATING SPRING-IN OF CURVED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Mechanisms responsible for spring-in are reviewed. Comparisons between experimental measurements and analysis show that the changes in angle due to thermoelastic effects on cooldown can be accurately predicted. Results are also presented showing how spring-in is affected by chemical shrinkage, tool-part interaction and part thickness. Shrinkage increases spring-in whilst tool-part interaction decreases it for external tooling and can even produce spring-out. The magnitude of both these effects increases with decreasing part thickness.

KEYWORDS: spring-in, curved composites, residual stress, shrinkage, tool-part interaction.

INTRODUCTION

Curved composites tend to change shape when cured, with an increase in curvature commonly referred to as spring-in. This can lead to difficulties in assembling composite structures, and increased costs. There has been considerable interest recently in this topic [e.g. 1-6]. This paper reviews the main mechanisms responsible for spring-in including thermal contractions, chemical shrinkage, tool-part interaction and corner consolidation, with comparisons between experimental measurements and model predictions.

THERMAL CONTRACTION ON COOLDOWN

The through-thickness expansion coefficient of composites such as carbon-epoxy is much higher than the in-plane expansion coefficients. This causes curved composites to spring-in on cooldown from cure. The effect is reversible, with the spring-in reducing if the part is reheated. This is referred to as thermoelastic spring-in, and is relatively well understood. The magnitude can be predicted from the equation:

$$\frac{\Delta\theta}{\theta} = (\alpha_l - \alpha_T)\Delta T \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta\theta$ is the change in angle θ , α_l and α_T are the in-plane and through-thickness expansion coefficients and ΔT is the change in temperature.

To investigate this mechanism, unidirectional L shaped parts were heated in an oven, and the change in the 90° angle measured. The parts were made from AS4/8552 with a lay-up of 0₄ and a thickness of 1 mm. They were laid up on the inside of an Invar tool with radius 20 mm,

where the 0° direction follows the curvature. The width was 100 mm and arm length 100 mm. A small mirror was mounted on the end of the specimen, and it was placed in an oven with a glass door. One arm was clamped to the base of the oven, with a second reference mirror attached. A laser was shone through the door on to the mirrors and projected onto a screen to measure the change in angle as the specimen was heated.

Fig. 1 shows the results for angle as a function of temperature. The response is linear, and the slope corresponds to a change in angle of 0.47° for a temperature change from 20° to 180°. Results were very repeatable.

Fig. 1: Thermoelastic response of L specimens

The in-plane expansion coefficient α_l from data supplied by Airbus is $0.02 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$. The transverse coefficient α_T was measured independently to be $32.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ using strain gauges [7]. Assuming transverse isotropy, and using this value for the through-thickness expansion coefficient in equation (1) gives a change in angle of 0.469° , the same as the measured result. Using laminated plate theory, the in-plane and through-thickness expansion coefficients for a $(0/90)_s$ cross-ply laminate were calculated to be $2.73 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $45.7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ respectively. Putting these into equation (1) gives a predicted spring-in of 0.619° , which again was found to be very close to the measured value of 0.63° , confirming the validity of the thermoelastic calculations.

CHEMICAL SHRINKAGE AFTER VITRIFICATION

Chemical shrinkage of the resin can be treated in the same way as thermal contraction, by adding an additional term to equation (1):

$$\frac{\Delta\theta}{\theta} = (\alpha_l - \alpha_T)\Delta T + (\phi_l - \phi_T) \quad (2)$$

where ϕ_I and ϕ_T are in-plane and through-thickness chemical shrinkages. This is a simplified version of the equation given by Radford and Rennick [1]. As discussed below, equation (2) is in fact only valid after vitrification, but can be used to calculate spring-in during this phase by taking ϕ_I and ϕ_T as the chemical shrinkage after vitrification. For many resins chemical shrinkage after vitrification is small. For the AS4/8552 material used here, this was studied by measuring the curvatures of unsymmetric cross-ply laminates during interrupted cure cycles [8]. Specimens which were rapidly quenched just after the material vitrified showed similar final curvature to those where the full cure cycle was completed. This shows that chemical shrinkage after vitrification is negligible for this material, and would not be expected to contribute to spring-in.

SHRINKAGE BEFORE VITRIFICATION

Most current models such as equation (2) do not distinguish between shrinkage before and after vitrification. However, in the phase between gelation and vitrification the composite is in a rubbery state, and can shear through the thickness. If it could shear freely, this would provide a mechanism to take up the change in circumferential length due to through-thickness contraction without inducing stresses in the fibre direction, eliminating any additional spring-in.

Fig. 2: Change of angle due to a through-thickness contraction

This is illustrated in Fig. 2. The schematics on the left show what happens when the material is stiff in shear, as it is when fully cured. With a through-thickness contraction while the part is constrained to the tool, there is no change in shape, and in-plane stresses are generated. When the part is released from the tool these stresses are released, and the part springs in. The schematics on the right illustrate the situation when the material is flexible in shear, as it is early in the cure. Now a through-thickness contraction leads to shearing of the part, with no in-plane stresses generated. There is therefore no spring-in, only through thickness shearing.

In practice the material is not completely free to shear and this has been treated by a new shear lag analysis [9]. If the rubbery shear modulus is high, or the composite is long compared with its thickness, the same result is obtained as with equation (2). However, as the shear modulus reduces, or as the length to thickness ratio decreases, the predicted amount of spring-in reduces.

Results are shown in Fig. 3 for AS4/8552 cross-ply laminates with different ratios of radius to thickness using a measured through-thickness shrinkage of 0.98% [10] and estimated through-thickness shear modulus of 43 MPa. The in-plane shrinkage was assumed to be negligible. When the thickness is large compared with the radius, the specimen is able to shear, and the predicted spring-in approaches the thermo-elastic value of 0.62° given by equation (1). As the thickness becomes small compared with the radius the predicted spring-in approaches the value of 1.50° given by equation (2).

This effect has been investigated experimentally by measuring spring-in of segments of 270° of cross-plyed $(0/90)_{ns}$ AS4/8552 tubes from 1 to 4 mm thick. They were cured on the inside of a 50 mm internal diameter carbon-fibre tube to eliminate any effects due to tool interaction. They were cured in an autoclave with the standard manufacturer's recommended cure cycle.

The outer diameters of the composite parts were measured at room temperature and equivalent spring-in angles were calculated for a 90° angle with respect to the tube inner diameter measured at 180°C using a ball nosed gauge. The diameters of the specimens were measured to within ± 0.01 mm, which should result in an error in spring-in within ± 0.02 degrees.

Fig. 3: Predicted shear lag effect on spring-in compared with results for different thicknesses

The results confirm the predicted trend of reducing spring-in with increasing thickness, with values varying from 1.31° at 1 mm thickness to 0.85° at 4 mm. The shear lag analysis correlates quite well with the experimental results. This influence of thickness on spring-in cannot be predicted at all by the simple equation (2).

It is the total change in through-thickness strain between gelation and vitrification that controls spring-in during this phase, including thermal effects. If gelation occurs at a lower temperature than vitrification, there will be a through-thickness expansion which will reduce the effect of chemical shrinkage. Both these components were included in the experimental value of shrinkage used here. Note that shrinkage before gelation will not contribute to this mechanism since the part geometry is only fixed when the resin gels.

TOOL-PART INTERACTION

The thermal expansion of many tool materials is higher than for the composite, causing the tool to stretch the part as a result of small shear stresses at the tool-part interface. Large stresses have been measured in unidirectional AS4/8552 flat plates during the cure due to this effect [11]. However, these stresses did not lead to significant distortion, as the stresses were apparently approximately uniform through the thickness.

If a stress gradient arises through the thickness, it will produce distortion that could either increase or decrease spring-in, depending which side the tooling is. On a curved part laid up inside an external tool fibres tend to wrinkle more on the inside radius, and so tension due to tool-part interaction is carried to a greater extent on the outside. This stress gradient opposes the effects of the other spring-in mechanisms, and can even cause spring-out in very thin parts.

Fig. 4: Effect of thickness on spring-in of unidirectional L sections

This is illustrated by results from the unidirectional L specimens mentioned earlier with different thicknesses. As well as the thermoelastic response, the total spring-in angles were measured with the help of a coordinate measurement machine. Straight lines were fitted to the

data from points at the ends of the radius to the ends of the arms to avoid the influence of arm bowing. Results are shown in Fig. 4 for specimens from 4 mm to 0.5 mm thick. The thicker two specimens gave similar results, but the 1 mm one showed a reduction in spring-in, whilst the 0.5 mm specimen actually sprang out. A similar trend was observed with cross-ply samples, although the magnitude of the effect was reduced.

The tool material was Invar, which still expands sufficiently to produce significant tool-part interaction. An even larger effect was found with an aluminium tool, with spring-out of as much as 16° measured in single ply L sections.

CONSOLIDATION

Consolidation due to resin flow and cure shrinkage prior to gelation cause reductions in thickness. The inextensible fibres tend to reduce this effect in curved sections cured on external tooling, leading to apparent corner thickening. This change of geometry can cause a small increase in thermoelastic spring-in, as can be seen from the results in Fig. 4. L sections 4 mm thick with corner thickening gave a thermoelastic spring-in of 0.50° compared with 0.47° for similar parts only 1 mm thick with relatively constant thickness. Although this is a fairly small effect, it was consistent. Cross-ply specimens with layup $(0/90)_{ns}$ exhibited a similar increase in spring-in from 0.63° at 1 mm thickness to 0.67° at 4 mm.

This difference can be predicted by finite element analysis taking account of the different geometry and volume fractions. Fig. 5 shows the model used, where the inner radius was increased to reproduce the corner thickness measured experimentally. Material properties were adjusted for the change in volume fraction using micromechanics equations and assuming the thickness change was all due to resin flow into the corner. The results showed an increase in predicted spring-in from 0.47° to 0.49° for unidirectional material and from 0.62° to 0.65° for cross-ply, close to the measured values.

Fig. 5: Finite element model of the effect of corner thickening on spring-in

There are also other more complex effects due to consolidation which are still not properly understood. Stresses may be set-up due to the autoclave pressure on inside radii being reacted by tension in the fibres, which can contribute to spring-in. Separation between the part and tool may occur in the corner despite the autoclave pressure, and can increase spring-in.

CONCLUSIONS

Thermoelastic effects on cooldown produce spring-in which can be predicted very well from the difference between in-plane and through-thickness expansion coefficients. The effect is increased slightly as a result of corner thickening, and this can be predicted by finite element analysis. Shrinkage between gelation and vitrification also contributes to spring-in. The magnitude is affected by shear lag, and therefore depends on the ratio of length to thickness and the interlaminar shear modulus of the gelled composite. This causes an increase in spring-in angle with reducing thickness for curved composites made on carbon-fibre tooling where there is no tool-part interaction. Wrinkling of fibres laid up inside a tool causes tension due to tool-part interaction to be carried to a greater extent on the outside. This reduces spring-in as the thickness decreases, and can even cause spring-out in very thin parts, the reverse of what happens due to shrinkage between gelation and vitrification. These opposing trends together with other factors relating to consolidation such as corner separation could explain some of the differences in spring-in measurements reported in the literature.

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